

1 **Large-Scale Wave-Driven Interactions and Plasma-Neutral Coupling**
2 **in the Low-Latitude Ionosphere-Thermosphere**

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17 **Key points:**

- 18 • Satellite observations of neutral and electron densities provide an excellent means to examine the
19 topside ionospheric response to wave driving in the lower atmosphere via large-scale wave structures.
- 20 • Correlation analyses revealed that tides act as a mediator for the interaction and coupling between
21 wavenumber structure patterns of density, which appear similar for narrow LT and magnetic LT
22 differences.
- 23 • CTMT results can generally explain the vertical coupling of the wavenumber structure of density
24 caused by upward propagating tides originating from lower and middle atmospheric sources.

25 **ABSTRACT**

26 The plasma and neutral density variations, interactions and coupling processes within $\pm 30^\circ$ latitudes are
27 examined concurrently by the DMSP-F18 and Swarm-C satellite during geomagnetically quiet years in 2020-
28 2021. The wavenumber (WN) patterns are computed in the form of neutral and electron density for two
29 altitudes and their latitudinal profiles are analyzed. We observe that the WN1 structure of the electron density
30 has a significant seasonal dependence in the topside ionosphere and dominates all other structures but WN2
31 neutral density amplitude dominates all other structures in the middle thermosphere (~ 440 km). Additionally,
32 we analyze vertical-temporal-latitudinal tidal structures from the Climatological Tidal Model of the
33 Thermosphere (CTMT) to find evidence for the modulation of the large-scale waves (LSWs) neutral density
34 structures. Through the examination of the in-situ observational and modeling approaches, we show that the
35 tidal contributors of WN structures obtained from CTMT can capture the influence of terrestrial sources on
36 the WN structures of plasma-neutral density and imprint the corresponding vertical coupling in the IT system.
37 Correlation analysis reveals that the amplitudes of the WN1 and WN3 structures of electron density in topside
38 ionosphere and those of neutral density in the middle thermosphere show intermittent but significant
39 correlations with each other, unlike the WN2 and WN4 structures. This study provides new insights into the
40 topside ionospheric response to wave driving in the lower atmosphere, which ultimately improves our
41 capability to understand the interaction and vertical coupling of large-scale structures, thereby advancing our
42 predictive capabilities of space weather critical for satellite operations.

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48 1. INTRODUCTION

49 Accurate understanding of the interaction between neutrals and plasma and their coupling via large-scale
50 waves (LSWs) in the ionosphere-thermosphere (IT) region is crucial for predicting and mitigating space
51 weather threats to satellite-based communication, and navigation, as well as radiation hazards to humans and
52 avionics systems. A broad range of temporal and spatial events (e.g., gravity waves, sudden stratospheric
53 warmings), generally modulated by solar and-magnetospheric sources, makes the IT region a highly unstable
54 system. Even without these intermittent-in-nature states, the IT system shows persistent variability that is
55 largely influenced by terrestrial weather. The LSWs of lower atmospheric origin (neutrals, plasma,
56 temperature, pressure, winds, etc.) most affecting the IT system have periodicities from 8 hours to a few days.
57 A significant subset of this wave variability generated in the tropical troposphere propagates to higher
58 altitudes, ultimately providing an opportunity for neutrals and plasma to interact and couple with each other.

59 Sun synchronous (non-Sun-synchronous) propagating tides are called migrating (nonmigrating) tides. This
60 usually leads to the formation of the effects of migrating tides in day-night variations and the effects of non-
61 migrating tides in the longitudinal variations. We used the widely adopted tidal notation (e.g. Hagan and
62 Forbes, 2002) for atmospheric tides in this study. As such, diurnal tides propagating eastward (westward) are
63 denoted by DEs (DWs), where the ends with their absolute magnitude, s , is the zonal wavenumber. Tides with
64 the zonal wavenumber positive integer 's' and negative integer 's' propagate westward and eastward,
65 respectively. Similarly, for semidiurnal tides, the D is replaced by an S. If tidal oscillations are zonally
66 symmetric, they are denoted by D0 (S0) for diurnal (semidiurnal) tides. The stationary planetary waves
67 (SPW) with a zonal number s are referred to as SPWs. Solar atmospheric tides, related to global-scale
68 variations of density, temperature, pressure, and wind waves with periods being solar day or their
69 subharmonics, are responsible for interaction and coupling the lower and upper layers of the atmosphere. A
70 variety of plasma-neutral coupling processes with a range of spatial and temporal scales cause the tropical
71 troposphere variability to be mapped into the IT system (Oberheide, et al., 2015; Gasperini et al., 2021). Due

72 to the unique configuration of electric and magnetic field lines near the equator, much of the IT response to
73 terrestrial weather occurs at low latitudes ($< 30^\circ$) and is driven by waves that are excited by deep convective
74 processes in the tropical troposphere and that propagate upwards into the IT system (Williams and Avery,
75 1996; Oberheide and Forbes, 2008; Khadka et al., 2016; Khadka, 2018; Gasperini et al., 2021). Tides can be
76 excited by orographic features (Forbes and Garrett, 1979), and by deep convective forcing where tidal
77 heating occurs because of cloud droplet formation (i.e., latent heat release during the vapor to liquid phase
78 transition). Another possible sources of nonmigrating tides are nonlinear interactions between stationary
79 planetary wave (SPW) and migrating tides or tidal/tidal interactions (Lieberman et al., 2004 and references
80 therein). Non-linear interactions in the neutral atmosphere with planetary waves generate child waves capable
81 of modulating amplitude of original or parent tidal waves (Yue et al, 2013; Chang et al., 2013). The upward
82 propagating waves present in the tropical troposphere, mesosphere/lower thermosphere (MLT) can impact
83 upper atmospheric temperature, wind, and composition structures (Krier et al., 2021; Gasperini et al., 2023).
84 Vertically propagating tides have profound influences on the transport of energy and momentum from their
85 sources into the MLT region (80 – 120 km altitude ranges) and beyond until they dissipate and deposit energy
86 and momentum into the background IT (Jones et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2021). As tidal waves propagate
87 vertically upward, their amplitudes increase with decreasing background atmospheric density to keep the
88 conservation of wave energy. The tidal energy is frequently redistributed among different tidal components in
89 some wave-wave interactions, but some components do not have enough spatial overlap to transfer energy.
90 For example, DE3, the most prominent nonmigrating tidal components, have mode interactions that transfer
91 energy within one tidal component, depending on background conditions (Zhang et al., 2012). A few waves
92 from the tropical wave system, which propagates and affects the IT system, tend to modify satellite drag
93 (Forbes et al., 2009; Oberheide et al., 2009; Gasperini et al, 2015, 2017) ionospheric densities (Chang et al.,
94 2011; Gu et al., 2014; Pedatella and Forbes, 2009; Gasperini et al., 2021), column number density (O/N_2)
95 ratio (Kil et al., 2013; Qian et al., 2022) F-region dynamo electric fields (Lin et al. 2007), and even GPS
96 signal fluctuations (S4 index) to a significant degree (Liu et al., 2013).

97 A significant portion of solar tides present in the thermosphere are originated in the lower and middle
98 atmosphere (Forbes, 2000; Hagan and Roble, 2001; Hagan and Forbes, 2002; Fritts and Alexander, 2003;
99 Huang et al., 2012) then propagated vertically from below or spread latitudinally via ducting within the
100 middle and upper atmosphere (McLandress, 2002; Jarvis, 2006; Zeng et al., 2008; Sato et al., 2009; Jones et
101 al., 2019; Wang et al. 2021). Some of these waves are also generated in situ by gravity waves or tides
102 modulated by planetary waves encountered at lower altitudes causing wave-wave interactions (Lawrence and
103 Jarvis, 2001, 2003; Smith, 2003, Jarvis, 2006). This global scale interaction and vertical propagation of
104 waves affects the local neutrals in the lower thermosphere and the local plasma in the ionosphere (Smith,
105 2012, Vincent, 2015; Yue et al., 2016; Triplett et al, 2019). Numerous modeling studies (Hagan and Forbes,
106 2002; Chang et al., 2008; Oberheide et al. 2011a; Yamazaki and Richmond, 2013; Fang et al., 2013),
107 observational studies from ground-based instruments (Forbes et al., 2000; Gong and Zhou, 2011; Huang et
108 al., 2012; Negrea et al., 2016), and satellite-based (McLandress et al, 1996; Mukhtarov and Pancheva, 2011;
109 Gasperini et al., 2015, 2022; Forbes et al., 2017) data analyses have focused on atmospheric tides and their
110 influence in the dynamics, structure, and variability of the IT system. Ground-based observations provide an
111 important perspective on the local behavior or short-term changes in tidal waves, whereas satellite
112 observations are the best way to examine global or large-scale structures and hence distinguish their different
113 tidal components in the IT system. Although the efforts of these studies made some progress on addressing
114 these topics, especially recent IT-dedicated satellite missions, detailed understanding on the role played by
115 upward propagating tides and their connection to the longitudinal structure of waves in the IT system is still a
116 dashing question to the science community. Due to the sparsity of concurrent global observations, the full
117 characterization of the sources of day-to-day variability of tidal waves of tropical tropospheric origin,
118 including nonlinear interactions, coupling between different atmospheric regions, and their impacts on the
119 low-latitude IT system, is very limited (Gasperini et al., 2022). If the E-region dynamo electric fields are not
120 dominated by changes in geomagnetic activity, the upward propagating tides are responsible for the
121 longitudinal variability but the effectiveness of these tides to produce longitudinal structures in the ionosphere

122 has yet fully to be determined (*Pedatella et al., 2008; Gasperini et al., 2018*). The modeling effort on this
123 case reveals that solar thermal tides generated in the troposphere can noticeably induce longitudinal
124 variability in the ionosphere *F*-region (*Hagan et al., 2007*) and if these tides are capable of inducing a
125 longitudinal structure in the dynamo electric fields, a similar type of structure should exist in ionospheric
126 electron density structures (*England et al., 2008*). The modulation of the neutral density in the middle
127 thermosphere by tides ultimately controls the formation of the ionospheric height. The collective effects of all
128 tidal components in producing significant longitudinal tidal variability depends on the constructive and
129 destructive interference and different vertical displacement effects that occur from one longitude sector to the
130 next (*Forbes, et al., 2008; Cahoy et al., 2006*).

131 Admittedly, the sources and physical mechanisms of interaction and coupling between plasma and neutral,
132 including forcing from above, below, and internal modifications, have been studied extensively from
133 observational and model perspectives for several decades, but the details on topside ionospheric response to
134 wave driving in the lower atmosphere is overlooked and coupling mechanism of LSWs via tidal waves in the
135 “IT gap” regions, particularly above 400 km, are still not clear. In addition, the mechanisms by which the tidal
136 signatures are manifest in the tropical troposphere are generally well defined, but their IT response is still
137 being debated. In the same vein, the availability of concurrent Defense Meteorological Satellite Program
138 (DMSP) and Swarm-C, a European Space Agency (ESA) Earth Explorer mission, satellite observations at two
139 different altitudes, 840 km and 440 km respectively, and an empirical model utilizing Hough Mode
140 Extensions (HMEs), and Climatological Tidal Model of the Thermosphere (CTMT) simulations during the
141 solar minimum and geomagnetically-quietest years (2020 and 2021) for similar F10.7 conditions, provides
142 an excellent opportunity to explore the topside ionospheric response to wave driving in the lower atmosphere.
143 The primary goal is to understand how global-scale waves and their interactions couple tropical tropospheric
144 variability with neutral and plasma density variability in the IT system. Most observational studies, including
145 those cited above, present very limited evidence of interaction and coupling between plasma and neutral in
146 global scales via terrestrial sources in the middle/upper thermosphere and topside ionosphere. Relative to

147 prior studies, our analysis extends the characterization of tides and their role in the interaction and coupling of
148 the large-scale wave structures of density from lower/middle thermosphere to the topside ionosphere using
149 DMSP data above 800 km altitude, i.e., much higher than most previous IT coupling studies focusing on
150 global-scale impacts at lower latitudes. Additionally, however, very limited work has been done on
151 investigating the WNS of density and their dynamics using satellites data, particularly of DMSP and Swarm
152 satellites, herein we extract wave number structures of neutral and plasma density from observations using a
153 Swarm-C and DMSP-F18 satellites respectively and examine their interactions and coupling using
154 contribution of the tidal components obtained from the CTMT model simulations. Notwithstanding under
155 nearly constant solar and geomagnetic activity levels, our analysis focusing on quiet periods emphasizes the
156 significance of lower atmospheric processes, particularly terrestrial sources. A correlation analysis has been
157 performed between the electrodynamics of the WNS of plasma in the topside ionosphere and those of the
158 neutral particles from the middle thermosphere, and then the level of correlation is quantified. We identify the
159 possible cause-effect factors for the vertical propagation of LSWs in the IT system from below at tropical
160 latitudes that trigger the variability, interaction, and coupling between plasma and neutrals.

161 The organization of this manuscript is as follows: in Section 1 we give an overview of related previous
162 studies, current research efforts to address scientific questions, some unanswered questions, and our efforts to
163 address these questions. Section 2 we describe the data sources, briefly overview these observational datasets,
164 the model used, analysis techniques, and the method of analysis. Section 3 provides details on the analysis
165 and the results revealed from the data and the model. Section 4 focuses on the discussion and interpretation of
166 the output from Section 3, and Section 5 summarizes the research investigation and the main conclusions.

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171 **2. DATA SOURCES, MODEL, AND APPROACH OF ANALYSIS**

172 The neutral and electron density measurements from Swarm-C and DMSP-F18 satellites, respectively, for
173 two years (2020 and 2021) solar quiet days are used to study the large-scale wave patterns and their role in the
174 interaction and coupling via thermal tides in the low-latitude region. Solar thermal tides are global-scale
175 oscillations, and therefore a satellite perspective of the tidal fields presents multifarious advantages (*Zhang et*
176 *al., 2006*). We discuss the in-situ DMSP-F18 and Swarm-C data processing techniques to calculate
177 wavenumber structures and to take advantage of the concurrent (same Universal Time but different
178 geographical locations) measurements of electron and neutral density at two different altitudes along their
179 ascending paths in the IT regions. Additionally, the diurnal and semidiurnal tidal components obtained from
180 the CTMT are used to interpret the interaction and coupling mechanism between plasma and neutral under the
181 aforementioned conditions.

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183 **2.1 BACKGROUND GEOMAGNETIC CONDITIONS**

184 Geomagnetic activity can be represented as the occurrence of K-variations (e.g., geomagnetic pulsations, bays
185 or substorms, sudden commencements, geomagnetic storms, etc.). The purpose of the Kp index, and derived
186 products are to monitor sub-auroral geomagnetic disturbances on a global scale which are particularly
187 important for space weather research and services (*Matzka et al., 2021*). This analysis focuses on the
188 geomagnetically quiet days during solar minimum years, 2020 and 2021. To specify the geomagnetic
189 condition, Kp and Ap indices are chosen. Due to the impact of the recovery phase of geomagnetic storm, the
190 tidal perturbation due to storms cannot completely be excluded by choosing low Kp values but their impacts
191 can be minimized. We selected geomagnetically quiet days (daily average $K_p \leq 3$) for analysis, aiming for
192 minimal perturbations due to the storm related influences on the large-scale structures of density. Figure 1(a)

193 and 1(b) show variations of these indices for 2 years and the flux density of solar radio emissions at a
194 wavelength of 10.7 cm that characterizes solar activity levels, respectively.

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196 **Figure 1 Geomagnetic Conditions:** (a) Day of the year (DOY) distributions of the daily average K_p index
197 (blue bars) and A_p index (magenta curves) for 2020 and 2021. The dotted horizontal line represents the
198 threshold line corresponding to K_p = 3, and (b) the noontime solar radio flux F10.7 shown in the bottom
199 panel. Only satellites data falling below the threshold line (K_p ≤ 3) are used for analysis in this project.

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205 2.2 OBSERVATIONAL DATA SOURCES

206 2.2.1 DEFENSE METEOROLOGICAL SATELLITE PROGRAM (DMSP)

207 The sparse study of the topside ionosphere (above 800 km) is generally due to limited data availability in
208 comparison with the lower part of the ionosphere (below 400 km). This deficiency is somewhat addressed
209 by a constellation, or a series of satellite launches in the Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP).
210 During its operation for over 50 years, numerous studies on the topside ionosphere have been carried out
211 using the DMSP data but there has been very limited analysis done from a tidal perspective. This program
212 provides strategic and tactical weather prediction to aid the US military in planning operations at sea, on
213 land and in the air. However, a significant number of satellites (F1 to F15 and F19) in the series of the
214 DMSP program have already been retired, leaving the currently operational in the series with the data
215 accessible from only three spacecrafts (F16 to F18), with different orbital altitudes and local times (*Kramer,*
216 *2002; Cai et al., 2019*). DMSP-F18 has two local times (LTs) of ascending (~17 Magnetic LT) and
217 descending (~05 Magnetic LT) nodes at the equator crossing that remain relatively constant throughout the
218 lifetime of the satellite and merely varies a few minutes during each year due to a slight non-uniformity in
219 the Earth's orbit around the Sun. The Air Force has flown the Special Sensor for Ions, Electrons and
220 Scintillation (SSIES) instrument package [*Hairston and Heelis, 1996; Hairston et al., 1998*] onboard the
221 DMSP spacecrafts in sun-synchronous near-polar orbits with an orbital period of about 101 minutes and
222 inclination near of 99° at altitudes near 840 km since the late 1980s. This instrument provides numerous
223 measurements, among others, of ion density. The DMSP electron/ion density data is publicly available via
224 the CEDAR Madrigal database and provides us an opportunity to study the possible interaction and
225 coupling between the topside ionosphere and middle thermosphere during the quiet days studies. In this
226 study, we use topside ionospheric electron number density (N_e) from the DMSP-F18 data, extract
227 wavenumber structures, and analyze its variations along ascending segments with respect to geomagnetic
228 coordinates under undisturbed conditions during solar minimum years.

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230 2.2.2 SWARM-C SATELLITE

231 The ESA's Swarm constellation mission for Earth Observation consists of three identical satellites, Swarm-A
232 (Alpha), Swarm-B (Bravo), and Swarm-C (Charlie). This constellation was launched in November 2013 into
233 near-polar circular orbits. Swarm-A and Swarm-C-orbit side by side at an altitude of ~450 km with an
234 inclination angle of 87.5°, and Swarm-B orbits at an altitude of ~510 km with an inclination angle of 88°
235 providing fully global coverage with a mean altitude that decreased to ~440 km by 2020. This constellation is
236 equipped with multiple instruments and provides precise simultaneous measurements of the magnetic field
237 and various ionospheric parameters over different regions of the Earth through a number of payloads onboard
238 each satellite (*Friis-Christensen et al., 2008*). Besides the primary research objectives of the Swarm mission,
239 which are investigations of the electrodynamics of the Earth's core to its magnetosphere and ionosphere,
240 mission data can also be used for space weather, climatology, modelling, and vertical coupling related studies
241 in the upper atmosphere (*Schrijver et al., 2015; Wood et al., 2022*).

242 Swarm-C carries onboard an accelerometer and GPS receiver package as part of its scientific payload that are
243 used to estimate total mass density (*Siemens et al., 2016*). For studying the dynamics of the upper atmosphere,
244 which results from a complex interaction between the charged particles and the neutrals in the ambient
245 magnetic field, the Precise orbit determination (POD) and Thermospheric Density and Wind (TDW) chains
246 suite on board of the Swarm satellites allow the derivation of the thermospheric neutral density of the upper
247 atmosphere (*Visser et al., 2013; van den IJssel et al., 2020*). The POD is necessary for geolocating the
248 observations taken by the scientific instruments on board of the Swarm satellites. The POD-derived neutral
249 density product is publicly available. For Swarm-C satellite, during 2020–2021, the local time at the
250 ascending and descending trajectories slowly drifts and takes around 133 to 135 days to cover all 24 hours of
251 local times. Swarm-C has a duration of about 90 minutes for one orbit and completes nearly 15 orbital cycles
252 every 24 hours. Referring to these orbital parameters, the satellite drifts about 2 hours local time every 11
253 days. We utilize the POD neutral density (in-situ, ~440 km) data from Swarm-C to derive large-scale wave

254 structure amplitudes for the ascending path (only along red traces in Figure 2) during solar minimum years
255 2020 and 2021.

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258 **Figure 2 Satellites paths about solar and magnetic local times at the equator:** Geometry of the satellite
259 tracks for Swarm-C (tilted lines) and DMSP-F18 (horizontal curves) satellites over the low-latitude ($\pm 10^\circ$)
260 region. The left vertical axis corresponds to Swarm-C whereas that in the right is for DMSP-F18 satellite data.
261 The red (blue) lines represent the ascending (descending) paths of the satellites during their equatorial
262 crossing. The ascending and descending paths are here chosen with reference to the argument of latitude and
263 magnetic LT (mLT) for Swarm-C and DMSP-F18 satellites respectively. Only satellite data corresponding to
264 ascending tracks of satellites are used for analysis to study day-to-day variability (see section 2.4 for details)
265 in this project. The narrow gaps in the curves represent either the unavailability of data points or are
266 intentionally suppressed to remove the off-pattern data.

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269 2.3 CLIMATOLOGICAL MODEL AND LIMITATIONS

270 We employed the Climatological Tidal Model of the Thermosphere (CTMT) (*Oberheide et al., 2011a*) to
271 elucidate the thermospheric variability resulting from upward propagating tides originated from below the
272 mesosphere lower-thermosphere (MLT) region/ lower atmosphere. This model is based on observations of
273 tidal temperatures and winds in the MLT region from the Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband
274 Emission Radiometer (SABER) and TIMED Doppler Interferometer (TIDI) instruments onboard the
275 Thermosphere Ionosphere Mesosphere Energetics Dynamics (TIMED) satellite, is extrapolated into the
276 thermosphere using HME modeling approach (*Forbes and Hagan, 1982; Svoboda et al., 2005; Forbes et al.*
277 *2014*), and provides the global behavior of vertically propagating tides in the thermosphere of the altitude and
278 latitude ranges of 0 to 400 km and pole to pole respectively. In this climatological model, the monthly 6 (8)
279 most important diurnal (semidiurnal) migrating and nonmigrating tidal components are obtained by compiling
280 an average of about 6 years (2002-2008) of the TIMED observations.

281 As outlined in *Oberheide et al., 2011a*, the CTMT is well-suited for contributions from solar radiation
282 absorption in the troposphere and stratosphere, tropospheric latent heat release, and non-linear wave-wave
283 interactions occurring in the MLT or below and is valid well for a low solar radio flux ($F_{10.7} = 110$ sfu)
284 conditions. Despite these performances, CTMT cannot capture the in-situ thermospheric tidal forcing via
285 migrating tides due to the absorption of solar EUV radiation, and nonmigrating tides by nonlinear interaction
286 processes. For example, the modulation of the migrating diurnal tides that produces nonmigrating tides as
287 secondary waves in the latter case due to the offset between the geographical and geomagnetic equator cannot
288 be incorporated in this model. The longitudinal ionospheric variability can produce significant D0 and DW2
289 tidal components through ion drag interactions involving the DW1 excited in situ in the thermosphere during
290 solar activity conditions (*Jones et al., 2013*). CTMT has been successful in interpreting the Michelson
291 Interferometer for Global High-resolution Thermospheric Imaging (MIGHTI) instrument on the Ionospheric

292 CONnections (ICON)-derived zonal and meridional wind diurnal/semidiurnal tidal amplitudes for viscous
293 dissipation and vertical coupling during solar low conditions (*Forbes et al., 2022, Gasperini et al., 2023*), but
294 without in situ sources of excitation due to tide-tide or tide-ion drag nonlinear interactions. Even though the
295 lower thermospheric tidal amplitudes are often larger in ICON/MIGHTI than CTMT, their structures and
296 seasonal variations are in good agreement (*Yamazaki et al., 2023*). CTMT tidal components have been used
297 and compared to many observational studies, in particular satellite observations (*e.g., Forbes et al.,*
298 *2012; Lieberman et al., 2013; Forbes et al., 2014; Forbes et al., 2022; Gasperini et al., 2023; Molina and*
299 *Scherliess,2023*). Along the same vein, we use contribution of 14 diurnal and semidiurnal components
300 obtained from CTMT to examine the role and contribution of terrestrial sources and forcing from bottom for
301 the scenario of amplitudes of wave number structures of densities derived from Swarm-C and DMSP-F18
302 data in the low-latitude IT regions for days with geomagnetic activity index K_p below or equal to 3 ($K_p \leq 3$).

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304 **2.4 EXTRACTION OF WAVE NUMBER STRUCTURES FROM SATELLITE DATA**

305 This subsection discusses how the large-scale wave structure of plasma and neutral density of satellite data
306 collected by the DMSP-F18 and Swarm-C satellites are extracted. Satellite observations are the best way to
307 study large-scale structures of density, temperature, wind in the upper atmosphere; and the data from these
308 observations can be used to examine the vertical, meridional, and zonal structures of tidal wave patterns
309 (*McLandress et al., 1996; Forbes & Wu, 2006; Zhang et al., 2006; Forbes et al., 2008; Wu et al., 2008;*
310 *Pirscher et al., 2010; Yuan et al., 2021; Gasperini et al., 2021, 2023, Yamazaki et al., 2023*). The results
311 presented here quantify the amplitudes of density wave structures in the upper atmosphere, based on the
312 following approach that we adopted.

313 In this investigation, we chose the solar minimum years of 2020 and 2021, select geomagnetically quiet days
314 ($K_p \leq 3$), and restrict only the ascending segments of satellite data for the analysis. For that purpose, the

315 Swarm neutral density and DMSP electron density data are categorized and processed for five different
316 latitudinal intervals, 20°N to 30°N , 10°N to 20°N , 10°N to 10°S , 10°S to 20°S , and 20°S to 30°S , which
317 are referred to as 25°N , 15°N , 0° equator, 15°S , and 25°S , respectively, in this manuscript. We have analyzed
318 the data and found that there is no significant difference in IT parameters between the 20° band at the equator
319 and other bands, which are 10° wide. The geographic and geomagnetic latitudinal intervals are chosen for
320 Swarm-C neutral and DMSP-F18 electron density data, respectively. This analysis focuses on solar and
321 geomagnetic quiescent conditions to examine the role of terrestrial sources to the IT coupling. For each of
322 those latitudinal intervals, the data corresponding to the days with daily average $K_p > 3$ are removed to
323 restrict the analysis to quiet conditions. Only satellites data falling under the threshold line ($K_p \leq 3$),
324 represented by the dotted horizontal line in figure 1 (a), are used for analysis. To simplify the data processing,
325 the next criterion for data selection is the range of the points where a satellite orbit crosses a reference plane.
326 For Swarm-C, the argument of latitude is taken as a reference to choose the ascending and descending paths.
327 The angle along the satellite orbit, measured from the ascending node, so that 0° and 180° correspond to the
328 ascending and descending equator crossings, respectively, while 90° and 270° correspond to the northern- and
329 southernmost points in the orbit is called argument of latitude (*Siemes et al., 2016*). Similarly, for DMSP-F18
330 satellites, magnetic local time (mLT) is considered as a reference to choose the ascending (17 mLT) and
331 descending (05 mLT) trajectories.

332 In general, tides are generated by the periodic heating of the Earth's daytime side atmosphere. Our analysis
333 focuses on daytime, and hence along the ascending path of the satellite when the mean neutral density is
334 largest, and the E-region dynamo is most effective (*Forbes et al., 2018; Immel et al., 2018*). To elucidate clear
335 pictures of interaction and coupling phenomena, we only use satellite data corresponding to ascending path
336 (along the red segments in figure 2) path of both Swarm-C and DMSP-F18 satellites. We use WN structures
337 on fixed LT space instead of tidal spectra to get day-to-day resolution. By considering only the ascending
338 node, the LT variation within the 15-day interval is negligible, and hence we approximate it to be constant.
339 Under the fixed LT approximation, migrating tides are largely absent in the WN fits, and the LT is not

340 considered to be a significant factor for non-migrating tides, which are the focus of this study. Furthermore,
 341 the satellite’s descending nodes (from the North Pole towards the South Pole) generally produce consistent
 342 results with those observed during the ascending nodes (from the South Pole towards the North Pole) with a
 343 12-hour phase difference. Further, data binning is done on a daily (for available days) basis. In each daily bin,
 344 there are at least 18 to 24 data points. To put it another way, we select one data point within each 60 to 90-min
 345 window to ensure that there are enough data points to evaluate wavenumber patterns. After this, we get a
 346 desired set of DOY profile of density for $\pm 180^\circ$ longitudes for the WN structure analysis. This provides
 347 complete longitude coverage, which is one of the requirements to extract tidal characteristics of large-scale
 348 wave structures. As we discussed above, global oscillations of solar tides of density fields induced by the
 349 daily cyclic absorption of solar energy show the period equal to subharmonics of solar day in the upper
 350 atmosphere. Those harmonics fits of density waves are done in longitude using equation (1) along ascending
 351 orbit node data. Then, the amplitudes of waves of zonal wavenumber 1–4 patterns (WN1–WN4) of neutral
 352 and electron density are evaluated using Swam-C and DMSP-F18 data, respectively.

353
$$y(\lambda)_{fit} = A_0 + \sum_{k=1}^4 A_k \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{360} k(\lambda - \varphi_k)\right) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

354 In the equation (1), the variable A_0 denotes the mean amplitude of density waves, λ denotes the longitude in
 355 degrees. A_k and φ_k represent the amplitude and phase of the density wavenumber k pattern, respectively.
 356 Different tidal components are included within each of the WN structures. A WN1 with fixed local time can
 357 be attributed either D0 or SW1. For instance, as presented in Table 1, WN4 represents the cumulative effect
 358 of DW5, DE3, SW6, SE2, SPW4, etc., which will be discussed in detail in the following sections.

359
 360 Importantly, during the fitting, we use the 15-day sliding window technique and compute amplitude of WN1
 361 to WN4 structures from electron and neutral density data. Applying this methodology to electron and neutral
 362 density measurements from the DMSP-F18 and Swarm-C, we evaluate the daily profile of amplitude of the
 363 WN structures for 2020 and 2021 using fit formula equation (1). The sliding window technique allows

364 systems to break down information into smaller blocks for more detailed analysis (*Jaén-Vargas et al.,*
365 *2022*). However, the basic approach to sliding window data processing is to recompute the specific window
366 slides, the data point within the window size might not be equally sampled in our case. This is because we
367 constrained the data set in various desired regimes, e.g., latitudes, quiet days, and ascending portion of
368 satellites for the analysis. Thus, the aim for choosing the 15-day sliding window technique is to ensure that
369 there are enough data points to accomplish the fit, reduce noise, and fill data gaps for nearly fixed local time.
370 While presenting the results, we further restrict the wave number profiles by choosing a threshold size for the
371 sliding window (15-day). If availability of data is only for 6 days (40%) or less in a 15-day sliding window,
372 the wave number structures are ignored for that case. The top two panels in figure 3 show the absolute WN1
373 to WN4 amplitudes patterns of (a) DMSP-F18 electron, and (b) Swarm-C neutral density in the geomagnetic
374 and geographic equatorial latitude region ($\pm 10^\circ$), respectively, for the two years using aforementioned
375 methods. The small breaks in the WN curves refer to data points below threshold of the size of window
376 separated by the dotted black line in the bottom panel of figure 3.

377 Further, the results presented in top panel of figure 3 show that the WN structures in the topside ionosphere
378 are dominated by WN1 most of the time and intermittently by WN4 whereas that in lower/middle
379 thermosphere, in second panel, are WN2 and WN4. Additionally, the periodicity of the large-scale
380 structures of both neutral and electron density are closely related to short-term periodic variation in solar
381 radiation which corresponds to approximately 27-day synodic rotation period of the Sun. At a first look, the
382 first panel in figure (3) shows that the absolute WN1 amplitude of electron density is the biggest compared
383 to all other amplitudes throughout the years. But the second panel in figure (3) demonstrates strong wave
384 number amplitudes WN2 and WN4 of neutral density during most of the time during both years, 2020 and
385 2021. It also seems that WN2 neutral density amplitude in 3 (b) dominates all other structures near February
386 and June in 2020 and May, June, and December of 2021. WN1 and WN4 become prominent towards the
387 end of both 2020 and 2021, while WN2 regained its leading role at the end of 2021. According to *Gamer et*

388 *al.* (2010), the DMSP-F18 plasma density above 200 cm^{-3} is valid. In contrast, *Visser et al.* (2013), report
 389 that comparisons with physical and empirical models indicate errors less than $\sim 11\%$ for Swarm satellite
 390 data. The driving factors behind this behavior of WN amplitudes structure of electron and neutral density in
 391 the equatorial latitudes will be discussed in the following sections.

392

393 **Figure 3 Wavenumber structures and the size of sliding window:** Absolute wave number amplitudes of
 394 (a) electron density (in units of $10^{10} / \text{m}^3$) from DMSP-F18 and (b) neutral density (in units of 10^{-13} kg/m^3)
 395 from Swarm-C satellites during equatorial ($\pm 10^\circ$) crossing along their ascending segment during
 396 geomagnetically quiet ($K_p \leq 3$) days of solar minimum years 2020 and 2021. The red, blue, cyan, and black
 397 curves in these panels represent the DOY versus amplitudes of the WN1, WN2, WN3, and WN4 of the
 398 density structures, respectively, evaluated from in-situ data measurements. The panel (c) shows the size of
 399 sliding window (15-day) throughout the investigation whereas the dotted black line represents the threshold
 400 (40%) of the size of moving window.

401

402 In fact, WN structures are superpositions of various tidal and stationary planetary waves. Referring to *Häusler*
 403 *and Lühr (2009)*, potential wave sources of the WN1-WN4 structures are summarized in Table 1. The shaded
 404 wave components in Table 1 are the potential sources of the WN1–WN4 structures available with CTMT
 405 outputs. The details on the superposition of the available wave components with CTMT and reconstructed
 406 WN1–WN4 structures are discussed in sub-section 3.3.

407

408 **Table 1: Contributing Tidal and Stationary Wave Components for Wavenumber Structures**

WN Patterns	Contributing Wave Components for WN Structures				
WN1	DW2	D0	SW3	SW1	SPW1
WN2	DW3	DE1	SW4	S0	SPW2
WN3	DW4	DE2	SW5	SE1	SPW3
WN4	DW5	DE3	SW6	SE2	SPW4

409 The shaded wave components in Table 1 are the potential sources of the WN1–WN4 structures available with
 410 CTMT.

411

412 **3 ANALYSIS AND RESULTS**

413 The structure, interaction, and coupling of large-scale waves (LSWs) in plasma and neutral densities are
 414 investigated using satellite observations at two different altitudes, topside ionosphere (~840 km), and middle
 415 thermosphere (~440 km) under identical conditions (similar latitudes and quiet days). Observation-based
 416 climatological tidal model studies have revealed that migrating and nonmigrating diurnal and semidiurnal
 417 tides from 80–400 km altitudes and pole-to-pole for moderate solar flux conditions have significant influences
 418 on interaction and vertical coupling of the large-scale structures. Even though many studies reveal evidence of
 419 the interaction and coupling of the LSWs, their sources, drivers, and propagation are still in debate. Our

420 analyses address such few questions with satellite measurement and from a modeling perspective. The focus
421 is on analyzing the contribution of terrestrial sources on the measured density wave structures in the low-
422 latitude IT system.

423

424 **3.1 DMSP-F18 ELECTRON DENSITY**

425 Referring to the method described in section 2.4, the absolute amplitude of wave number structures during
426 solar minimum years (2020 and 2021) derived from DMSP-F18 in-situ measurement of electron density data
427 at altitudes of 840 km for quiet days in the low-latitude (within 30°N - 30°S) sector along ascending segment
428 of satellite path are presented as a surface contour plot in Figure 4. From top to bottom, the four panels in
429 Figure 4, display the WN1 to WN4 variations, respectively, as a function of geomagnetic latitudes and day of
430 the year (DOY) of 2020 and 2021. Similar to the electron density WN amplitudes presented in figure 3(a) for
431 equatorial latitude interval, 10° N to 10° S (for 0°), we evaluate all (WN1 to WN4) amplitudes using equation
432 (1) for other latitudinal intervals, 20° N to 30° N, 10° N to 20° N, 10° S to 20° S, and 20° S to 30° S that
433 correspond to the amplitudes for +25°, +15°, -15°, and -25°, respectively. These amplitudes of electron
434 density WN amplitudes are collectively presented as contour subplots in figure 4.

435 It can be inferred from the top panel of Figure 4 that the WN1 displays higher values than other WN patterns
436 during summer season in both northern and southern hemispheres. An antisymmetric structure can clearly be
437 seen in the magnitude of WN1 strengths and seems to follow seasonal patterns. A stronger WN1 is seen
438 extended into the northern hemisphere on and around June solstice and then into the southern hemisphere
439 during December solstice. This characteristic follows the fact that the Southern (Northern) hemisphere is in
440 summer season during December (June) solstice, and the hemisphere experiencing summer receives the most
441 solar radiation due to the longest period of daylight. A clear trend of increased WN structures of electron
442 density in the northern summer hemisphere during solstices compared with that in winter hemisphere is
443 evident throughout two year's WN1 profiles. Solar activity rises and falls with an 11-year cycle that affects

444 ionospheric plasma density as well as the intensity of geomagnetic activity. The bottom panel of Figure 1
445 shows the two-year patterns of solar radio flux F10.7, which is a common proxy for the level of
446 photoionization in the earth's ionosphere, that is increasing from 2020 towards 2021. Also, strength of WN1
447 follows the trend of the amount of ionization caused by higher solar irradiance in the summer season, which
448 occurs in June (December) in the northern (southern) hemisphere. These results strongly support the fact that
449 the WN1 structure of the electron density has a significant seasonal dependence in the topside ionosphere.

450 The second panel of Figure 4 shows the latitudinal profile of WN2 structure of electron density for 2020 and
451 2021. WN2 seems to have equatorial symmetry with some sort of periodicity. Similarly, the third and bottom
452 panels show the latitudinal profile of WN3 and WN4 of electron density for 2020 and 2021. In most of the
453 cases, these profiles are equatorially symmetric, and maxima occur near southern hemispheric summer
454 throughout the years. The sources and controlling factors behind the large-scale WN amplitudes structure of
455 electron density will be discussed in detail in section 4.

456

457

458 **Figure 4 WNS from DMSP-F18:** The DOY versus magnetic latitude distribution of the absolute amplitude
 459 of the wave number structures of electron density obtained from DMSP-F18 observations at 840 km altitude.
 460 Each panel (1st – 4th) from top to bottom represents the contour (DOY versus magnetic latitude) subplot of
 461 WN1-WN4 structures, respectively, in the low-latitude ($\pm 30^\circ$) region. These contour subplots are obtained by
 462 applying 15-day moving windows and including only geomagnetically quiet ($K_p \leq 3$) days data
 463 corresponding to ascending paths (along red lines in figure 2) of the satellite.

464

465 3.2 SWARM-C NEUTRAL DENSITY

466 Applying the method mentioned in section 2.4, the absolute amplitudes of the WN1-WN4 are extracted
 467 using equation (1) from Swam-C neutral density data for altitude range of 440 km. We evaluated all (WN1
 468 to WN4) amplitudes for the geographic latitudinal intervals, 20° N to 30° N, 10° N to 20° N, 10° N to 10° S,
 469 10° S to 20° S, and 20° S to 30° S that correspond to the amplitudes for $+25^\circ$, $+15^\circ$, 0° , -15° , and -25° ,

470 respectively. These neutral-density WN amplitudes are represented as geographic latitude vs DOY contour
471 subplots in Figure 5, which shows the distribution of the data at the low-latitudes. In order to highlight the
472 equatorial latitudinal profiles of neutral density waves without any loss of information, we presented the
473 amplitude variations in the symmetric parts of WN structures about the equator along the ascending path in
474 figure 5. We then evaluate the daily symmetric WN amplitudes of neutral density by summing the WN
475 amplitudes in northern latitudes with those corresponding to southern latitudes, and then dividing the result
476 by 2 to eliminate the antisymmetric components for ascending tracks of the satellite. Figure 5 characterizes
477 the amplitude of WN structures obtained from neutral density observed in the middle thermosphere and the
478 concurrent structure of electron density in the topside ionosphere is in figure 4. Figure 5 shows the latitudinal
479 profile of WN structures of neutral density for 2020 and 2021 and the profiles exhibit both symmetric as well
480 as antisymmetric characteristics at different periods. The amplitudes of WN structures seem stronger in 2021
481 than during 2020. In May, June, July, and December of 2021, the amplitude of WN2 is equatorially
482 symmetric and becomes stronger than that of other periods of the year. Also, right after June of 2021, WN4
483 increases abruptly for the three months of 2021. It can be inferred from figure 5 that amplitude of WN2
484 neutral density dominates all other structures in 2020 and 2021.

485

486

487 **Figure 5 WNS from Swarm-C:** Same contour (DOY vs Geographic latitude) subplot of WN1-WN4
 488 structures as figure 4 but for neutral density data observed from Swarm-C satellite at 440 km altitude after
 489 highlighting symmetric structures.

490

491

492

493 3.3 TIDAL COMPONENTS FROM CTMT

494 We investigated diurnal and semidiurnal tidal variability in neutral density from the CTMT model to elucidate
 495 the relative contribution of the tidal components in the WN structures obtained from Swarm-C and DMSP-
 496 F18 data. We present the latitude-temporal structures of 6 diurnal and 8 semidiurnal components of tidal
 497 density amplitude near 110 km and 400 km altitudes because diurnal and semidiurnal tides are more

498 predominant than other components. It is to be noted that CTMT only accounts for contributions from solar
499 radiation absorption in the troposphere and stratosphere, tropospheric latent heat release, and non-linear wave-
500 wave interactions occurring in the MLT or below. CTMT is unable to reproduce in-situ-forced migrating tides
501 resulting from solar EUV forcing (e.g., the middle thermospheric DW1), and in-situ-forced nonmigrating
502 tides in the middle thermosphere due to nonlinear interactions, most notably the diurnal nonmigrating tidal
503 components DW2 and D0 that are likely forced by ion drag interactions at high latitudes (*Jones et al., 2013*).
504 Figure 6 shows the contour plots of 6 diurnal and that of 8 semidiurnal in figure 7 tidal density amplitudes at
505 (a) 110 km and (b) 400 km altitudes in the latitude versus month of the year (MOY) domains estimated from
506 the Climatological Tidal Model of the Thermosphere (CTMT). The variability of six diurnal components
507 (DW2, DW1, D0, DE1, DE2, and DE3) on latitude vs MOY is shown in figure 6, and the variability of eight
508 semidiurnal components (S0, SE1, SE2, SE3, SW1, SW2, SW3, and SW4) is shown in figure 7. These
509 components are evaluated from CTMT and quantitatively demonstrated for two altitudes, (a) 110 km and (b)
510 400 km.

511 From figure 6, it is seen that the CTMT diurnal amplitude of relative density structures DE2, DE3, and DW2
512 reflect significant degree of symmetry about the equator at 110 km but DW2 is more symmetric at the lower
513 heights (110 km) and more antisymmetric at the higher heights (400 km). The relative density is the ratio of
514 the absolute density to the mean density, the annual and global mean densities are obtained from MSIS. The
515 amplitude of equatorially symmetric DE3 is stronger than all of these. Further, the latitudinal distribution of
516 DE3 centered near the equator is wider than other symmetric structures at 110 km as well as 400 km altitudes.
517 Evidently, there is no significant change in the latitudinal structures of symmetric components of DE2 and
518 DE3 tides at 110 km and at 400 km altitudes. It can be speculated that these tides propagate vertically into the
519 thermosphere without suffering dissipation due to their longer vertical wavelengths. Primarily, D0 is
520 antisymmetric about the equator and shows large maxima around $\pm 30^\circ$ latitude at 110 km which is further
521 shifted toward the polar latitudes at 400 km altitude. The antisymmetric structure of DW1, the equatorial
522 component at 110 km vanishes as one moves upward at 400 km.

523 (a) CTMT diurnal amplitudes of density at 110 km altitude

524

525 (b) CTMT diurnal amplitudes of density at 400 km altitude

526

527 **Figure 6 Diurnal Tidal Components from CTMT:** Latitude versus month of the year (MOY) contours of
528 diurnal amplitudes of density expressed in relative tides at (a) 110 km and (b) 400 km obtained from CTMT
529 are shown. Diurnal tides, DE1, DE2, DE3, D0, DW1, and DW2 are depicted in those plots for both altitudes.

530

531 An example of semidiurnal tidal signatures in the density is presented in figure 7, which generally shows
532 their peak amplitudes at higher latitudes/altitudes. The semidiurnal amplitude structures of density are nearly
533 antisymmetric about the equator at both altitudes, 110 km, and 400 km, except SW4 which shows symmetric
534 about equator at 400 km. SE1 has peak amplitudes at equator and at/around $\pm 60^\circ$ latitude during summer at
535 both altitudes, 110 km, and 400 km. S0 amplitudes maximize at the poles whereas that of SW1 and SE2
536 maximize in the mid-latitude range. The maxima of SW3 occurs during equinox. Overall, the strength of
537 SW2 dominates all other amplitudes at both altitudes of the analysis.

538

539 (a) CTMT semidiurnal amplitudes of density (%) at 110 km altitude

540
541

542 (b) CTMT semidiurnal amplitudes of density (%) at 400 km altitude

543

544 **Figure 7 Semidiurnal Tidal Components from CTMT:** Latitude-MOY contours of semidiurnal amplitudes
545 of density expressed in relative tides at (a) 110 km and (b) 400 km altitudes obtained from the CTMT are
546 shown. For semidiurnal tides, SE1, SE2, SE3, S0, SW1, SW2, SW3, and SW4 are depicted in those plots for
547 both altitudes.

548

549 As listed in Table 1, the potential sources of WN1–WN4 are identified as tidal oscillations DW2, D0, SW1,
550 SW3 and SPW1 for WN1; DW3, DE1, S0, SW4, and SPW2 for WN2; DE2, DW4, SE1, SW5, and SPW3
551 for WN3; and DE3, DW5, SE2, SW6 and SPW4 for WN4. We have reconstructed WN1–WN4 from
552 corresponding potential sources available with CTMT. In the latitude versus MOY profile in figure 8 shows
553 the superposition of contributing CTMT component of tidal oscillations for WN1 to WN4 at 110 km and 400
554 km altitudes. Only 11 tidal components obtained from CTMT are used for superposition plots in figure 8.
555 DW1, SE3, and SW2 are absent from depictions since CTMT provides 14 diurnal and semidiurnal
556 components. Comparing 8(a) and 8(b), the WN4 is seen equatorially symmetric at 110 km but these patterns
557 change to antisymmetric at 400 km altitude. But the nature of WN3 is exactly opposite i. e., antisymmetric at
558 110 km but somewhat symmetric at 400 km. The reconstructed WN amplitudes in figure 8 and their
559 comparison with the observed amplitudes are discussed in the following sections.

560 Figure 8 suggests that the combined effect of migrating and nonmigrating tides are important for tidal
561 modulation of the WN structures in the low latitude IT system. In terms of CTMT tidal components (shaded
562 part in Table 1), WN1 is the aggregate effect of two diurnal (DW2, D0) and two semidiurnal (SW1 and SW3)
563 components. These components are antisymmetric about the equator at 110 km and this anti-symmetry
564 becomes clearer at 400 km. Similarly, WN2 and WN3, which have DE1, S0, and SW4 and DE2 and SE1 as
565 potential sources respectively, are antisymmetric but the symmetric structure of WN3 is noticeable at 400 km.
566 Interestingly, superposition of DE3 and SE2 generates equatorially symmetric WN4 structure at 110 km
567 altitude that shifts towards the polar latitude at 400 km altitude, giving it an antisymmetric shape.

568

a) Superposition of amplitudes of WN contributors at 110 km altitude

569

570

b) Superposition of amplitudes of WN contributors at 400 km altitude

571

572 **Figure 8 Superposition of CTMT Tidal Components as Sources of WN structures:** A combined CTMT
573 tidal components as potential sources of WN structures are depicted along latitude vs. MOY contour plot, (a)
574 for 110 km and (b) for 400 km altitudes. CTMT tidal oscillations D0, DW2, SW1 and SW3 are superposed
575 for WN1. Similarly, DE1, S0, and SW4 are superposed for WN2; DE2 and SE1 for WN3; and DE3 and SE2
576 for WN4.

577

578 **4 INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION**

579 Previous studies (e.g., *Miyahara et al. 1993*; *Oberheide and Forbes, 2008*; *He et al., 2011*; *Chang et al.,*
580 *2011*; *Gu et al., 2014*; *Oberheide et al., 2015*; *Yigit et al., 2016*; *Forbes and Roble, 1990*, *Forbes et al.,*
581 *2021*; *Lieberman et al., 2022*; *Gasparini et al, 2015, 2021, 2023*) demonstrated that upward propagating
582 waves of tropospheric origin can have remarkable influences on interaction and coupling between large-scale
583 wave structures in the low-latitude IT system. CTMT density (*Oberheide et al., 2009*) and temperature
584 (*Forbes et al., 2014*) tides have already been extensively tested and validated with Challenging Minisatellite
585 Payload (CHAMP) satellite data. Although our study is restricted to $\pm 30^\circ$ latitude, obvious evidence of
586 modulation of the WN structures by the diurnal and semidiurnal migrating tides has been found in the lower
587 thermosphere. It is useful to remember that this manuscript is about the WN structures evaluated from
588 DMSP-F18 and Swarm-C observations with CTMT as a tool to identify the effect of upward propagating
589 tides. We use CTMT output as latitude-temporal structures (14 diurnal and semidiurnal components) of tidal
590 density amplitudes at 110 km and 400 km altitudes. The principal influence of D0, DW2, SW1 and SW3
591 creates the WN1 structure. Referring to figure 6, D0 is strongly antisymmetric about the equator at 110 km
592 and such structure shifted towards polar latitude in CTMT and are not confined to low and middle latitudes.
593 The aggregate effect of these tidal wave components likely forms the antisymmetric structure of WN1
594 (figure 8) which can also be seen in the WN1 structures of electron density in DMSP-18 (figure 4) and the
595 neutral density in Swarm-C (figure 5) data. DW2 and D0 have upper thermospheric sources and are

596 generated in-situ by a nonlinear interaction of DW1/SPW1 type (*Oberheide et al., 2011a*) whereas DW1 has
597 a strong dependency on solar activity and season/latitude (*Gasperini et al., 2023*). SE2 can propagate from
598 the troposphere. The middle/upper thermospheric DW2 is mostly due to magnetic/geographic pole
599 displacements (from DW1, SPW1 interactions). A combined effect of DE1, S0, and SW4 contributes to
600 WN2. Both CTMT and Swarm-C results show antisymmetric structure of WN2.

601 The contributors DE2 and SE1, account for the WN3 as the CTMT outputs in figure 8. DE2 is a highly
602 symmetric structure at both altitudes, 110 km, and 400 km. Whereas SE1 tidal structure is more
603 antisymmetric with respect to the equator at 110km as well as at 400 km. Overall, Swarm-C neutral density
604 WN2 amplitude is also seen antisymmetric in structure. The DE2 tide is mainly generated by (i) latent heat
605 release associated with deep tropical convection and (ii) nonlinear interactions between migrating and non-
606 migrating tides (*England, 2011*). From CTMT output perspective, the superposition of DE3 and
607 SE2 is responsible for WN4. As seen in figures 6 and 7, DE3 is symmetric and SE2 is antisymmetric at both
608 altitudes, 110 km, and 400 km. In figure 8, WN4 seems symmetric at 110 km even though it
609 is antisymmetric at 400 km and gives an impression to depend on season/MOY. It can be said that DE3 is a
610 major contributor to the WN4 at 110 km altitude and can effectively propagate to the middle thermosphere.,
611 but SE2 takes the lead over DE3 at 400 km altitude. This is due to the higher frequency and the longer
612 vertical wavelength of SE2 since this reduces the effects of dissipation compared to a diurnal tide (*Oberheide*
613 *et al., 2011a, 2011b*). The strong symmetric WN4 structures of electron and neutral densities were also seen
614 during similar period in figure 4 and 5. Compared to all the individual tidal components, DE3 is the largest
615 and is now known to produce significant ionospheric effects (*Forbes et al., 2008*). The antisymmetric
616 structure of WN4 obtained from Swarm-C has been shifted toward higher latitudes in northern hemisphere
617 which is clearly captured by the WN4 pattern of CTMT during August-September. In general, our CTMT
618 results for the major potential sources of WN structures are qualitatively consistent with the satellite data.

619

620 **Figure 9 WN patterns in fixed mLT and different LT at Low Latitudes:** Comparative patterns of relative
 621 WN amplitudes of DMSP-F18 electron density (eD) at 17 mLT and Swarm-C neutral density (nD) at different
 622 LT (16, 18, 20, 23) along ascending paths, i.e. one hour earlier, 1 hour, 3 hours, and 6 hours later than mLT,
 623 respectively, within $\pm 10^0$ latitudes in 2020. The patterns exhibit similarity when there is a narrow difference
 624 between LT and mLT in most cases. Data gaps in the plot refer either unavailability of data or $K_p > 3$ days.

625

626 Referring to figure 2, in figure 9, we choose the DOY 213 to 301 period in 2020 of mLT and LT ascending
 627 crossing node of the DMSP-F18 and Swarm-C satellites at low latitude ($\pm 10^0$) to observe the patterns of
 628 relative amplitude of electron and neutral density. Each row in figure 9 shows the 7-day comparative plot of
 629 the relative WN1 to WN4 amplitudes of DMSP-F18 electron density (eD) and Swarm-C neutral density (nD)
 630 in LT one hour earlier, 1 hour, 3 hours, and 6 hours later than mLT, respectively. Excluding the 6 hours LT

631 and mLT difference and those 3 hours difference for WN2, the patterns do not change much. Specifically, one
632 can confirm from figure 9 that if Swarm-C LT is one hour earlier than or one hour after the DMSP-F18 mLT
633 along ascending path in the equatorial crossing of the satellites, the relative WN amplitude patterns look
634 similar. The LT of the observed points on the ascending and descending orbit portions of a satellite is nearly
635 independent of longitude (*Oberheide et al., 2002, Lieberman et al. 2004*). During the years 2020-2021,
636 Swarm-C, with its slow precession orbit, covers approximately 24 hours of local time in a span of 133-135
637 days, considering both ascending and descending nodes. Consequently, these LT variation cycles are unlikely
638 to significantly contribute to errors in the tidal extraction (*Gasparini et al., 2015; 2017*). When focusing
639 solely on the ascending node of the satellite, it is reasonable to assume a fixed local time within moving
640 windows for nonmigrating tidal extraction. Migrating tides, on the other hand, primarily arise from variations
641 in the source and background atmosphere, as well as in situ forcing. The solar in situ forcing of migrating
642 tides for dynamical changes in the upper thermosphere is not much more important than their upward
643 propagating tidal components (*Maute et al, 2023*).

644

645 To investigate how the topside ionosphere responds to WN structures of neutral density and tidal components
646 in the lower/middle thermosphere, we use two data sources, one providing topside ionospheric observations
647 from DMSP-F18 and the other middle thermospheric observations from Swarm-C. We evaluate the Pearson's
648 correlation coefficients between the WN structures in DMSP-F18 electron density and the Swarm-C neutral
649 densities and then inspect the role of their potential tidal contributors of WN structures using CTMT
650 results. The correlation coefficient is a statistical measure of linear dependence of two random variables, and
651 the Pearson correlation coefficient is commonly used for the estimation of these parameters. It is difficult to
652 accurately quantify correlation between parameters in the highly variable ionosphere that is involved in the
653 complex process of interactions and IT coupling. Therefore, we have chosen 60-day moving windows for the
654 analysis of correlation coefficients, i.e. fourfold of moving windows (15-day) for WN structures analysis. The

655 evaluated correlation coefficients between the WN structures of Swarm-C neutral density and the DMSP-F18
656 electron density are depicted in figure 10 for 60-day moving windows in $\pm 10^\circ$ latitudes. We define a threshold
657 value of ± 0.3 for correlation coefficients that are considered insignificant and not correlated well. Conversely,
658 correlation coefficients greater than or equal to ± 0.6 are considered significant correlations.

659 There is strong evidence for the propagation of waves from 110 km to exosphere and can be measured tidal
660 components, DE3, DE2, D0, SE2, SE3, and SE1. DW2, S0, SW4, and additional components are generated as
661 in-situ excitation components. (e.g., DW2, SW6) in the exosphere temperature (*Forbes et al., 2014*).
662 Therefore, during the course of vertical propagation, these tidal components play a vital role in the interaction
663 and coupling between WN structures in the middle thermosphere to topside ionosphere as their potential
664 contributors. In terms of correlation coefficients, strong interactions can be defined as the coexistence of
665 strong positive and negative correlation values among the interacting waves, such as tides, gravity waves, and
666 planetary waves (*Huang et al., 2012*).

667

668 **Figure 10 Correlation coefficients:** Correlation coefficients between the electron and neutral density WN
669 structures within $\pm 10^0$ geographic latitudes under sliding windows of 60-day sizes are shown. The red, blue,
670 cyan, and black curves represent the correlation coefficients between the WN1, WN2, WN3, and WN4 of the
671 DMSP-F18 electron and Swarm-C neutral density structures, respectively. We only consider positive
672 correlation, which denotes the pattern of two variables moving in the same direction and is a suitable
673 parameter to explain interactions and vertical coupling phenomena. Negative correlation coefficient values
674 that refer to anti-correlation are set to null. The dotted horizontal lines represent correlation coefficient values
675 equal to 0.6 and beyond that is considered as strong correlation between interacting wave WN structures.

676

677 In Figure 10, the amplitudes of the WN1 structure of Swarm-C neutral density and DMSP-F18 electron
678 density waves have very similar variations and intermittently highly correlated with more positive correlation
679 events in 60-day windows. The significant positive correlation of WN1 is seen in March and April of both
680 years, in June and July of 2020, and in August of 2021. Referring to Table 2 of *Truskowski et al. 2014*,
681 spectra for the diurnal (D0 and DW2) and semidiurnal (SW1 and SW3) tides which are some of the
682 contributors of WN1 are excited by both lower atmospheric heating as well as by non-linear wave-wave
683 interactions. With this scenario, we may infer that the WN structures of electron density in topside ionosphere
684 and those of neutral density in the middle thermosphere are highly correlated if their contributors as tidal
685 components are excited by lower atmospheric heating, wave-wave interactions, and in situ excitation together.

686 From figure 10, it can be perceived that for WN2, correlation is significant with positive values during March
687 equinox and northern summer in 2020 but such patterns can be seen nearly end of 2021. Notably, the
688 correlation between amplitude of the WN3 of Swarm-C neutral density and DMSP-F18 electron density is
689 seen to possess almost equal, continuous, and significant positive correlation coefficient values during first 5
690 months of 2021.

691 The WN4 structures of electron density and that of neutral density show occasional positive correlation events
692 with less than 0.6 value except during end of 2021. The longitudinal WN4 structure in the ionospheric F
693 region originates from the symmetric modes of the DE3 tide in the ionospheric E region (*Wan et al., 2010*).
694 Even though DE3 is symmetric at the equator (figure 6), the combined effect of contributing tides for WN4 at
695 higher altitude (figure 8b) becomes antisymmetric. It can be suggested that if the vertical profile of
696 contributing tidal components of WN structures is changing, weaker correlation is prevailed. For other
697 intervals, correlation on WN structures occurs occasionally but not significantly.

698

699 **5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION**

700 This study leads to a considerable advance in the study of the large-scale wave-driven interaction and
701 plasma-neutral coupling in the low-latitude “IT gap” region. It also laid a few open and unresolved questions
702 for future study. The outcomes presented here delineate how the wave number structures of thermospheric
703 neutral density and topside ionospheric electron density interact with each other and respond to tidal
704 components originating from the tropical troposphere. The tidal components obtained from an empirical
705 climatological model display many characteristics related to interaction and coupling between the observed
706 large-scale wave structures in this investigation. The major outcomes from our study are summarized as
707 follows.

- 708 1. Satellite observations of the WN structures of neutral and plasma density are the best way to examine
709 large-scale structures in the ionosphere-thermosphere (IT) system. The WN structures of Swarm-C
710 neutral density in middle thermosphere and that of electron density measurement in the topside
711 ionosphere from DMSP-F18 show the interaction and coupling processes between two altitudes.

712

713 2. The WN1 structure of the electron density has a significant seasonal dependence, like DW1, which is an
714 interacting part of SPW1 that ultimately generates D0 and DW2 after interaction in the topside
715 ionosphere. The antisymmetric patterns can clearly be seen in the magnitude of WN1 structure of electron
716 density and seems to follow seasonal patterns in the low-latitude region. The stronger WN1 is seen
717 extended into the northern hemisphere on and around June solstice and then into the southern hemisphere
718 during December solstice. This characteristic follows the fact that the Southern (Northern) hemisphere is
719 in summer season during December (June) solstice. The latitudinal profile of WN3 and WN4 of electron
720 density for 2020 and 2021 look equatorially symmetric, and maxima occur near southern hemispheric
721 summer throughout the years.

722

723 3. It also seems that WN2 neutral density amplitude dominates all other structures at around June solstice
724 but WN1 and WN4 start to become prominent near the end of 2021. DE3 tides, which suffer less
725 dissipation during vertical propagation, are the main contributor for WN4 structures at 110 km, but SE2
726 takes over its role at 400 km and can produce significant effects in the IT system.

727

728 4. The performance of the CTMT is an excellent model to explain vertical coupling phenomena caused by
729 upward propagating tides from tropospheric sources with certain shortcomings. Even though all potential
730 contributors of WN structures are not incorporated in CTMT, the available tidal components of CTMT
731 can characterize the interaction and coupling process between WN structures. Notably, CTMT may
732 overcome its limitations by assimilating Swarm-C data to better replicate the in situ forced tides.

733

734 5. This study confirms that tides act as key agents of interaction and coupling between the large-scale
735 wavenumber structure of neutral density in the lower thermosphere and the electron density in the topside
736 ionosphere. If Swarm-C LT is one hour earlier than or one hour after the DMSP-F18 mLT along
737 ascending path in the equatorial crossing of satellites, the relative WN amplitude patterns look similar.

738 WN structures of electron density in topside ionosphere and those of neutral density in the middle
739 thermosphere are highly correlated if their contributors as tidal components are excited by lower
740 atmospheric heating, wave-wave interactions, and in situ excitation together in the low-latitude region.

741

742 6. Comparison of observation and model reveal that the diurnal and semidiurnal nonmigrating tides
743 propagate directly upward from their terrestrial source regions, which can modulate the WN structures in
744 the low-latitude IT region creating the constructive and destructive interference effects among potential
745 sources of the WN structures along their vertical propagation.

746

747 7. There is a remarkable (>0.6) but intermittent correlation between WN structures of Swarm-C neutral
748 density and DMSP-F18 electron density. Amplitudes of the WN1 and WN3 structures have significant
749 correlation events than that of the WN2 and WN4 throughout 2020 and 2021 in 60-day sliding windows
750 analysis.

751

752 To sum up, this study highlights the importance of the “IT gap” region and attempts to examine the topside
753 ionospheric response to wave driving in the lower atmosphere from tidal perspectives. Simultaneous and
754 multi-satellites observations improve the capability to resolve large-scale features and understanding
755 interaction and vertical coupling in the “IT gap” from tropospheric sources to advance our abilities on satellite
756 operations and space weather. More research efforts of IT phenomena are necessary to improve space
757 situational awareness (SSA) to secure and advance technology-based modern society. Meanwhile, NASA’s
758 upcoming missions, the Geospace Dynamics Constellation (GDC), consisting of six satellite constellations is
759 scheduled to be co-launched with the Dynamical Neutral Atmosphere-Ionosphere Coupling (DYNAMIC)
760 mission around 2030 which are aimed to investigate basically how and why tidal weather vary, respectively
761 (*Oberheide et al., 2023*). These missions will undoubtedly make significant progress in addressing not only

762 how terrestrial weather processes produce space weather effects but also in providing insights to update and
763 improve current modeling approaches in the IT system for the heliophysics community.

764

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771

772 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

773 Datasets and climatological model used in this study are publicly available. The geomagnetic Kp index, Ap
774 index, and F10.7 Solar Radio Flux data are available at <https://kp.gfz-potsdam.de/en/data>. The DMSP ion
775 density data are available via the CEDAR Madrigal Database at <http://cedar.openmadrigal.org/>. The Swarm-C
776 Precise Orbit Determination (POD)-derived neutral density product are available at
777 <http://thermosphere.tudelft.nl/>. The neutral density data from the Swarm-C satellite pertinent to this paper can
778 be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11107142> (Khadka, 2024). CTMT is available from
779 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5541913> (Oberheide, 2011).

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